

COPYRIGHT AND LICENCES in Diamond Open Access publishing

What information to display, where and how: a short guide for journal publishers.

Copyright owner

- Author instructions
- Dedicated copyright and/or Open Access pages
- Publishing contracts/agreements (if applicable)
- Open Policy Finder + Directory of Open Access Journals databases
- Full text of the work/paper.
- Metadata description of the work

Licensing policies

- Author instructions
- Dedicated copyright or Open Access pages
- Publishing contracts or agreements (if applicable)
- Open Policy Finder and Directory of OA Journals databases
- Journal pages of the publishing service's platform

Licences

In all formats of the articles (e.g. PDF, HTML):

- Name of the Licence
- Licence icon. e.g. *the CC logos*
- Hyperlinks to the full legal text of the licence. e.g. *"This work is Licenced under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence](#)."*
- Short descriptive text in the article. e.g. *"You are free to share and adapt this work, but you must give appropriate credit and distribute your contributions under the same Licence"*

In the metadata description in the article:

- Name of the Licence
- URL to the licence text
- In the metadata submitted when registering article persistent identifiers (DOI, ARK, URN, etc.)

Guidelines for third-party copyright

Requirements for authors:

- Obtain necessary permissions
- Properly cite all third-party content
- Include separate Licence information if needed

General best practices

- **Clarity is key:** write precise and easy-to-read content.
- **Machines matter:** ensure accurate and properly formatted metadata.
- **One policy, all platforms:** maintain consistent policies across journals and platforms.
- **Legal harmony:** copyright and licensing should not contradict each other.
- **Stay up-to-date:** regularly review and update policies.

